

Chemical speciation studies on aurintricarboxylic acid complexes of Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} in solution phase : A prerequisite for analytical determinations

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Abstract : Chemical speciation studies of the binary complexes of Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} with aurintricarboxylic acid (ATA) (a tetradentate ligand with five possible binding sites) have been carried out pH metrically in aqueous medium at constant ionic strength and temperature. Best fit chemical models representing the metal complexes with different compositions were obtained using MINIQUAD75 computer program. Mono nuclear species of the type MLH₂, MLH, ML and ML₂ were found to exist in solution for all the three metals. The species distribution diagrams for three metals were generated using HYSS program. The results show that the type and percentage form of the complexes formed have a strong dependence on pH and the overall stability constants are greater for Ga^{III} compared to Al^{III} and In^{III}.

Keywords : Chemical speciation, aurintricarboxylic acid, stability constants, group IIIA elements, distribution diagrams.

Introduction

Aurintricarboxylic acid (5,5'-((3-carboxy-4-oxocyclohexa-2,5-dienylidene)-methylene)bis(2-hydroxybenzoic acid)) (ATA) is a reddish orange crystalline solid soluble in water and strong alkalies and is an important compound known for biological activity, anti HIV activity¹, anti viral activity, a potent inhibitor of nucleic acid processing enzymes². It is also used as an anti apoptotic drug to counteract ischemic or cytotoxic injury to neurons³ and in the effective treatment of beryllium poisoning⁴. Using ATA against influenza-A post infection has a strong protective effect by inhibiting virus ability. ATA reacts with metal ions to form coloured complexes which are soluble in water. Several reports were published in literature on the use of ATA as a selective and sensitive chromogenic reagent for spectrophotometric or spectrofluorimetric studies⁵⁻⁷. However its

metal-ligand equilibria and speciation with Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} have not been studied so far.

Results and discussion

Proton-ligand equilibria of ATA :

Knowledge of the distribution of protonated species of the ligands as a function of pH is important to understand the various interactions that exist in a solution containing metal and ligand. Information of acid dissociation constants is essential, since pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic properties change with the pK_a values. They are also used to predict bioavailability⁸. Though ATA is a ligand of pharmaceutical and biological importance, there are very few reports on the pK_a values of ATA. Banerjee and Dey⁹ and Avinashi *et al.*¹⁰ reported two protonation constants while Hasan Atabey *et al.*¹¹ reported five protonation constants in aqueous medium.

As a prelude to the study of stability constants of Group IIIA elements Al, Ga and In with ATA, we have determined the protonation constants under the present experimental conditions. ATA consists of three aromatic moieties. Two of these moieties are α -hydroxy carboxylic acid systems which contain two donor groups, the hydroxyl and carboxylate group. The third moiety is α -oxo carboxylic acid which contains only one donor group. It contains three carboxyl protons and two hydroxyl protons groups, therefore acid-base equilibria may contain LH, LH₂, LH₃, LH₄ and LH₅ type of species in the solution.

The data obtained from the pH metric titrations described in the Experimental section was subjected to analysis by the MINIQUAD75¹². The protonation constants were obtained in two methods; in the first, the pH metric data were used to refine the protonation constants of each experiment, while in the second the pooled data were used (Table 1). The best fit model was selected based on the statistical parameters. A very low standard deviation in log β values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (the sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of ligand and hydrogen ion at all experimental points corrected for degrees of freedom) indicate that the model can represent the experimental data. Five formation constants β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , β_4 and β_5 , were obtained for ATA. The formation constants β_1 , β_2 correspond to enolic protons, while β_3 , β_4 and β_5 correspond to carboxylic protons.

Metal-ligand equilibria :

Data processing and selection of best fit model :

In this investigation, the ligand to metal ratio is greater than or equal to unity and hence only mono nuclear complexes are assumed to be exist. The expected binary complexes are ML, MLH, MLH₂, ML₂, MLH₃, ML₂H₂ and ML₂H₄. The preliminary screening of species resulted in ML, MLH, MLH₂ and ML₂ species. Various models for different ligand to metal ratios were analysed using MINIQUAD75

Fig. 1. Distribution diagrams of binary complexes of ATA with Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III}.

Table 1. Best fit chemical model for acido-basic equilibria of ATA in aqueous medium
Temp. = 25.0±0.1°C, Ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³, pH range = 2.0–11.0

Expt. No.	log β ₁ (SD)	log β ₂ (SD)	log β ₃ (SD)	log β ₄ (SD)	log β ₅ (SD)	NP	U _{corr} × 10 ³	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ ²	R
1.	9.01(2)	17.98(0.4)	23.43(2)	26.89(2)	29.88(2)	109	0.11	-0.69	8.98	33.96	0.00072
2.	8.94(3)	17.90(0.6)	23.89(5)	27.42(5)	30.55(5)	100	0.11	0.91	5.31	35.84	0.00079
3.	9.05(2)	17.37(1)	23.09(3)	26.70(3)	29.54(3)	76	0.03	0.67	4.28	31.79	0.00061
4.	9.00(4)	17.42(1)	23.26(4)	26.90(4)	29.47(4)	89	0.04	0.07	4.98	22.63	0.00056
Average	9.00(3)	17.67(0.75)	23.42(4)	26.98(4)	29.86(4)	94	0.07	0.24	5.89	31.01	0.00067
Pooled	8.95(4)	17.85(1)	23.84(4)	27.34(5)	30.36(4)	397	2.80	-0.40	15.5	272.8	0.00394

U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) × 10⁸, where m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points.

program. Best fit models based on statistical parameters were obtained in two ways. In the first approach, the experiments corresponding to the three metal to ligand ratios were used individually. In the second approach all data of the three ratios of metal to ligand were taken together (pooled data). The stability constants thus obtained are given in Table 2.

The statistical parameters taken into consideration are skewness, kurtosis, crystallographic R-value and standard deviation. The residuals (the differences between the experimental data and the data simulated based on model parameters) are around zero mean

with little dispersion indicates that the model is said to be adequate. For an ideal normal distribution, the values of skewness and kurtosis should be 0 and 3, respectively. The values of skewness between -0.65 and 2.89 suggest that the residuals form a part of normal distribution; hence, the least squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the lower crystallographic R-values compared to those obtained by statistical treatment.

The order of stability of the complexes is Al < Ga > In. Stabilities of Ga species are found to be

Table 2. Best fit chemical model for metal ion-ATA systems in aqueous medium
Temp. = 25.0±0.1°C, Ionic strength = 0.16 mol dm⁻³

M : L Ratio	log β _{mlh} (SD)				NP	U _{corr}	Skewness	Kurtosis	χ ²	R
	1 1 0	1 1 1	1 1 2	1 2 0						
Al ^{III} (pH 2–10)										
1 : 1	—	14.46(33)	—	12.27(34)	25	0.0314	1.76	4.55	37.53	0.057
1 : 2	—	—	22.75(59)	10.32(56)	95	0.8237	2.62	7.76	71.56	0.115
1 : 3	—	—	26.04(15)	12.26(15)	90	0.1964	2.06	6.12	160.7	0.070
Pooled	5.89(41)	—	22.32(45)	10.33(46)	288	1.14	2.78	9.71	593.11	0.197
Ga ^{III} (pH 2–6)										
1 : 1	—	22.16(7)	—	—	121	0.038	0.12	2.78	76.78	0.015
1 : 2	—	21.88(9)	—	24.41(14)	118	0.064	0.68	2.83	56.12	0.021
1 : 3	—	21.19(14)	—	22.64(27)	113	0.114	0.69	2.74	65.55	0.024
Pooled	14.68(8)	—	26.06(6)	—	330	0.0181	1.57	8.98	327.03	0.010
In ^{III} (pH 2–9)										
1 : 1	12.17(3)	18.38(1)	22.83(2)	—	71	0.00009	-0.65	4.43	87.36	0.0012
1 : 2	—	16.98(8)	23.29(5)	15.58(12)	60	0.00215	0.17	5.72	71.91	0.0029
1 : 3	—	—	23.78(8)	—	57	0.0148	2.89	15.4	175.25	0.0047
Pooled	11.56(14)	18.06(18)	23.96(7)	—	289	0.0218	0.04	7.13	409.08	0.0117

U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) × 10⁸, where m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points.

greater than those of Al and In, due to several factors like ionic size, coordination number, hard-soft nature and geometric factors. Group IIIA ions are hard acids, favour oxygen donors and show predominantly covalent bonding. Al forms six membered chelate where as Ga and In forms five membered rings. All the three metal complexes form six membered chelate in this study. Hence covalent radius of the metal plays major role in stabilizing the complexes. Similarly the electronegativity is the highest for Ga among three metals. This explains highest stability of Ga^{III} .

Species distribution plots :

Using the $\log \beta$ values the species distribution diagrams were generated using HYSS¹³ program (Fig. 1). In the case of Al^{III} -ATA system, AlLH_2 , AlL and AlL_2 species exist in the pH range 6.0 to 8.6. The species AlLH_2 is formed by the reaction between free metal and LH_3 at a pH of 6.0 which is confirmed by the decrease in the concentrations of free metal and LH_3 and an increase in the concentration of AlLH_2 . The species AlL is formed by the reaction of free metal ion with LH_2 . The species AlL_2 can be obtained by the reaction of AlLH_2 with either LH_2 or LH at a pH of 8.2 and 8.6, respectively. The species AlL and AlL_2 are formed simultaneously and their percentages increase with increase in pH.

In the case of Ga^{III} -ATA system, GaLH_2 and GaL are formed in the pH range of 2.6 to 4.6. The species GaLH_2 is formed in two ways, i.e. the reaction of free metal ion with LH_5 and LH_4 at a pH of 2.8 and 2.6, respectively. The species GaL is formed in two different ways i.e. the reaction of free metal ion with LH_3 and the deprotonation of GaLH_2 at a pH of 4.1 and 4.6, respectively.

To verify the presence of the species, LC-MS for the reaction mixture of 1 : 2 metal to ligand molar concentration ratio was recorded (Fig. 2). The spectral analysis is again speculative without any experi-

mental proof. A molecular peak at 989.5 was found, might be due to a 1 : 2 (M : L) complex. The corresponding species distribution diagram is given in Fig. 3.

In the case of In^{III} -ATA system, the species InLH_2 , InLH and InL are formed. The species InLH_2 is formed by the reaction of free metal ion with LH_3 at a pH of 4.2 and InLH is formed by the reaction of free metal ion with LH_3 at a pH of 5.2 and deprotonation of InLH_2 at pH of 6.0. InL can be formed by the deprotonation of InLH at a pH of 6.5.

The results show that the type and percentage of the major form of the complexes have a strong dependence on pH. The Al^{III} complexes are formed in the pH range 6.0 to 8.6, Ga^{III} complexes are formed in the pH range 2.8 to 4.6 and In^{III} complexes are formed in the pH range 4.2 to 6.5.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to rely upon the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under various experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was made by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters such as concentrations of alkali, mineral acid, ligand and metal (Table 3).

The magnitudes of stability constants are influenced by errors in the concentration of alkali, acid, ligand and metal; some species were rejected when these errors were introduced. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the choice of the best-fit models.

Experimental

Reagents :

Solutions were prepared using doubly glass distilled water through which nitrogen was gas purged to expel any dissolved oxygen or carbon dioxide. A $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of ATA (Sigma-Aldrich, India) was prepared. All other chemicals were used of analytical grade. Metal ion solutions Al^{III} , Ga^{III}

Fig. 2. LC-MS of Ga-ATA (1 : 2).

and In^{III} , $2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ (Sigma-Aldrich, India) concentrations were prepared from the corresponding chlorides and were standardised by conventional complexometric titrations. An overall 0.05 mol dm^{-3} acid was maintained in all the metal ion solutions to repress the hydrolysis. A $\sim 0.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ solution of sodium hydroxide was prepared and standardized against potassium hydrogen phthalate. It was then regularly Gran-titrated^{14,15} to check the

absence of carbonates. Solution of 0.02 mol dm^{-3} hydrochloric acid, prepared by successive dilutions was standardised against a standard solution 0.02 mol dm^{-3} of sodium hydroxide solution which was prepared from the standard stock solution. To maintain the ionic strength (0.16 mol dm^{-3}), 2 mol dm^{-3} sodium chloride (Merck, India) solution was prepared.

Fig. 3. Species distribution diagram of Ga-ATA (1 : 2).

Equipment :

Potentiometric titrations were carried out by using Metrohm 877 titrino plus auto-titrator (Switzerland) (readability 0.001) in conjunction with a com-

bination electrode (0–14 pH range) for pH measurements at a temperature of 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. The pH meter was calibrated with 0.1 mol dm^{-3} potassium hydrogen phthalate solution (pH = 4.01) in acidic region and 0.05 mol dm^{-3} borax solution (pH = 9.18) in basic region.

Data acquisition and analysis :

The main objective of chemical speciation study is determination of composition and extent of formation of various species containing metal ion(s) and ligand(s) under the given set of conditions of temperature, ionic strength and pH and also used to calculate the concentrations of all the species present in the solution including the free metal ion and free ligand at any given experimental point.

Calvin-Wilson titration technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti^{16,17} was used for the study of protonation and complex equilibria of the ligand (ATA). Requisite volumes of hydrochloric acid (to give an overall concentration of $2.0\text{--}4.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$), sodium chloride (to maintain the ionic strength 0.16 mol dm^{-3}) and ligand ($1.25\text{--}7.25 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ in different experiments) in the absence and presence of a metal ion, in a total volume of 50.0 cm^3 were titrated with $\sim 0.02 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ sodium hydroxide at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. In different experiments the initial metal to ligand molar concentration ratios were maintained at 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3. After the addition of each aliquot (0.05 cm^3) of sodium hydroxide, the pH meter data were automatically saved by the instrument. The effect of variations in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode were accounted for in the form of correction factor by using SCPHD¹⁸ program.

Conclusions

ATA has three aromatic moieties with two α -hydroxy carboxylic groups, each containing two donor groups. The third has α -oxo carboxylic acid con-

Table 3. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the In^{III} -ATA complex stability constants

Chemical component	% Error	$\log \beta_{\text{mlh}}$ (SD)		
		1 1 0	1 1 1	1 1 2
Alkali	0	11.57(14)	18.06(18)	23.96(7)
	-5	Rejected	16.27(20)	22.79(16)
	-2	Rejected	17.47(13)	23.50(7)
	+2	13.33(16)	18.63(39)	24.34(8)
	+5	15.55(17)	Rejected	24.79(10)
Acid	0	11.57(14)	18.06(18)	23.96(7)
	-5	15.44(17)	Rejected	24.87(10)
	-2	13.13(17)	18.62(35)	24.36(7)
	+2	10.18(22)	17.42(16)	23.52(8)
	+5	Rejected	16.47(20)	22.87(16)
Ligand	0	11.57(14)	18.06(18)	23.96(7)
	-5	11.69(14)	17.96(22)	23.95(7)
	-2	11.62(14)	18.03(20)	23.95(7)
	+2	11.51(14)	18.08(17)	23.96(6)
	+5	11.43(14)	18.10(16)	23.97(6)
Metal	0	11.57(14)	18.06(18)	23.96(7)
	-5	11.57(14)	18.07(19)	23.98(6)
	-2	11.57(14)	18.07(18)	23.96(7)
	+2	11.56(14)	18.05(18)	23.95(7)
	+5	11.56(14)	18.04(18)	23.94(7)

taining only one donor group. Stability constants of ATA complexes of Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III} were determined pH metrically using MINIQUAD75 program. Species distribution diagrams indicate the formation of MLH₂, MLH, ML and ML₂ type of species. The results showed that stability constants of Ga complexes are greater than those of Al and In which can be explained on the basis of covalent radii and electronegativities. Since the values of stability constants and dependence of formation on pH are distinctly different for each of the metals, ATA can be used as a suitable reagent for sensitive and selective separation of Al^{III}, Ga^{III} and In^{III}. Thus this study can form a prerequisite for analytical determination.

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